

A Retrospective Cohort Study on the Treatment of Giant Cell Tumors in Knee Joint Bones using Sequential Curettage, Cauterization, Cementation, and Implant Fixation

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Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 26-06-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Giant cell tumors of bone often occur around the knee, and since most patients have long-term survival, there is a significant demand for maintaining limb function. The ideal treatment method for such cases is controversial. This study was done to evaluate the radiological and functional outcomes of treating GCT of the distal femur and proximal tibia through extended curettage, chemical cauterization with phenol, cavity filling with bone cement, and fixation with screws or a locking plate.

Methods: This retrospective observational cohort study was carried out between 2015 and 2022. Preoperatively patients were evaluated clinically and radiologically. Magnetic resonance imaging was done in all the cases to know the extent of tumour. FNAC was conducted of all the patients and after confirmation of GCT, surgery was performed. Demographic and clinical data were noted. The MSTS 93 score had been used for functional evaluation at the last follow-up in our study. The patients were followed up for a mean period of 2 years (range 1–3 years).

Results: Eighteen patients met the inclusion criteria, with a mean age at surgery of 31.3 years (range 18–65 years). Most patients (71.7%) were in their third and fourth decades of life. There was a slight predominance of males, with a male-to-female ratio of 1.25:1 (10 men and 8 women). The study included 8 cases involving the distal femur and 10 cases involving the proximal tibia. Campanacci grade III was seen in six cases, grade II in ten, and grade I in two cases. The average follow-up period was 2 years (range 1–3 years). Chemical cauterization was performed in all cases. No instances of recurrence or pathological fracture were noted. Furthermore, there were no cases of metastasis or malignant transformation seen during the study. The mean MSTS 93 functional score at the last follow-up was 25.8.

Conclusions: This study concludes that while the distance between cement and subchondral bone may predict future arthrosis, it does not affect functional outcomes. Based on these findings, we recommend extended intralesional curettage, cauterization, and cementation with implant fixation following GCT curettage. This approach offers ease of implementation, best recovery of limb function, a low short-term recurrence rate, and high patient acceptance in clinical practice. With a median follow-up of 30 months in this study, further research involving larger cohorts and longer follow-up periods is called for in the future.

Keywords: GCT, Extended Curettage, Cauterization, Bone Cement, Implant.

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Introduction

Giant Cell Tumor (GCT) comprises 5% of all primary bone tumors and 20% of benign bone tumors. It primarily affects individuals aged 20 to 40 years and is slightly more prevalent in females. Although benign, GCTs are aggressive, with a high rate of local recurrence and low metastatic potential. Patients with recurrent lesions or aggressive primary lesions (stage 3) are at higher risk for lung metastases, which occur in approximately 3% of cases. GCTs most commonly develop in the long bones, particularly the distal femur, proximal tibia, and distal radius, together

accounting for 50% of cases. [1] Tumors in the distal radius are more aggressive than those in the distal femur and proximal tibia.

Campanacci et al. classified GCTs into three types based on their biological behaviour, radiographic appearance, and degree of bone destruction. Type I lesions are latent and small, confined within the bone. Type II lesions are active and larger, with an intact periosteum. Type III lesions are aggressive, extending beyond the periosteum into surrounding tissues. [1] Patients usually present with swelling and progressive pain, initially related to activity but

later occurring at rest. Occasionally, patients remain asymptomatic until a pathological fracture occurs. Active lesions (Grade 2) are the most common, accounting for approximately 60% of cases. The diagnosis of GCT involves radiographic imaging and confirmatory histology. Standard radiographs typically show eccentrically located lytic lesions in the epiphysis of long bones, often with poorly defined transition zones. Less aggressive tumors may exhibit a partial rim of reactive bone. The lesion often expands or breaks through the cortex, although intraarticular extension is rare due to the intact subchondral bone. The center of the lesion may show a soap-bubble appearance. MRI is useful for assessing the lesion's extent within the bone and soft tissue. On MRI, the lesion appears dark on T1-weighted images and bright on T2-weighted images. MRI may also reveal fluid-fluid levels indicative of a secondary aneurysmal bone cyst, present in 20% of cases. (Figure 1)

Histologically, GCTs consist of three cell types: mononuclear histiocytic cells, osteoclast-like multinucleated giant cells (typically 40 to 60 nuclei per cell), and neoplastic stromal cells, which constitute the main proliferating cell population. The nuclei of the mononuclear histiocytic cells are identical to those of the giant cells, distinguishing GCTs from other tumors with many giant cells. Secondary aneurysmal bone cysts may also be present.

Most GCTs present as stage 2 or stage 3 lesions. Historically, treatment was simple curettage, which had a recurrence rate of over 50%. With MRI, the extent of lesions can be more accurately assessed, improving curettage techniques. Adjuvants like liquid nitrogen, phenol, bone cement, electrocautery, or an argon beam coagulator aid in eliminating residual tumor cells, thereby reducing recurrence rates to 5%-15%. The primary treatment for GCT of bone is intralesional curettage. En bloc excision and amputation are reserved for recurrent or recalcitrant cases. Surgeons typically use intralesional resection for Campanacci grades I and II, while for Campanacci grade III, en bloc resection followed by reconstruction is performed. [2,3]

To fill the defect after curettage, surgeons can use autograft bone, allograft bone, artificial bone graft substitutes, or methyl methacrylate bone cement. Bone grafts restore bone stock, remodeling along stress lines according to Wolff's law, providing permanent reconstruction, restoring normal joint biomechanics, and preventing degenerative joint disease. [4] However, bone grafts have two main disadvantages: (1) prolonged joint protection to prevent pathologic fractures, and (2) difficulty distinguishing tumor recurrence from graft resorption.

These issues can be addressed using bone cement as a filling agent. Bone cement provides immediate stability, facilitating quicker rehabilitation, and allows easier detection of recurrence, manifesting as an expanding radiolucency next to the cement mantle. The heat of polymerization from the cement may also help eradicate residual tumor cells. Cement is suitable for defects of all shapes and sizes. However, the main drawback of curettage and cementation alone is the high fracture risk due to insufficient fixation and early loading of the bone. [5] The difference in elastic modulus between the cement and normal bone can lead to gradual bone absorption and loosening of the cement, known as the "ball effect." Thus, internal fixation is often necessary when using cement.

This study was done to evaluate the radiological and functional outcomes of treating GCT of the distal femur and proximal tibia through extended curettage, chemical cauterization with phenol, cavity filling with bone cement, and fixation with screws or a locking plate.

Methods

This retrospective observational cohort study was carried out between 2015 and 2022 at the Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences, a tertiary-level institution located in Patna, Eastern India. Patients underwent preoperative clinical and radiological evaluations, including magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) to determine tumor extent. Fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) confirmed the diagnosis of GCT prior to surgery. Inclusion criteria were: (1) Definite pathological diagnosis of GCT, (2) GCT involving the distal femur or proximal tibia, (3) no prior treatment for the tumor, and (4) complete clinical, radiographic, and pathological records. Written informed consent was obtained from all patients prior to their inclusion in the study. The following data were recorded for each patient: tumor side (left or right), tumor location (distal femur, proximal tibia), Campanacci stage (grade I, II, or III), presence of pathological fracture (yes or no), and details of surgical treatment (intralesional curettage, application of PMMA cement, and implant fixation). All procedures were performed following approved guidelines.

Surgical Technique: The tumor area was extensively exposed, and a large bony window was created corresponding to the lesion size. Thorough curettage was performed followed by chemical cauterization with phenol. After extended curettage, autologous iliac crest bone graft was used to cover subarticular areas in smaller lesions, and screws were employed to secure the cement within the bone.

For larger lesions, periarticular locking plates were fixed to the shaft and filled with bone cement after

drilling tracts for screw passage through the metaphysis and epiphysis. The cement was molded anatomically, excess cement in the soft tissue was removed, and the wound was closed in layers.

Functional Evaluation: At the final follow-up, functional outcomes were assessed using the MSTS 93 score. [6] This score evaluates patient activity, including pain, function, emotional acceptance, walking ability, and gait, on a 5-point scale for each variable, with a maximum score of 30 points indicating better functional outcomes. The mean follow-up period was 2 years (range 1–3 years).

Results

Eighteen patients met the inclusion criteria, with a mean age at surgery of 31.3 years (range 18–65

years). The majority of patients (71.7%) were in their third and fourth decades of life. There was a slight predominance of males, with a male-to-female ratio of 1.25:1 (10 men and 8 women). The study included 8 cases involving the distal femur and 10 cases involving the proximal tibia. Campanacci grade III was observed in six cases, grade II in ten, and grade I in two cases.

The average follow-up period was 2 years (range 1–3 years). Chemical cauterization was performed in all cases. No instances of recurrence or pathological fracture were noted. Furthermore, there were no cases of metastasis or malignant transformation observed during the study. The mean MSTS 93 functional score at the last follow-up was 25.8.

Figure 1: (A) Clinical photograph of a Case showing swelling on medial side right knee. (B) Preoperative X-ray 6 weeks prior to surgery (C) Preoperative X Ray (D-E) MRI films showing the extent of lesion

Figure 2: Serial radiographs. (A) Post-operative X-Ray. (B) X ray at 6 weeks (C) X ray at 6 months

Figure 3: Serial radiographs of 2nd Case (A) Preoperative X-ray (B) Post-operative X Ray (C) X ray at 6 weeks (D) X ray at 6 months (E) X ray at 1 year

Discussion

Intralesional curettage is the primary surgical approach for treating GCTs, despite its association with a high local recurrence rate (5-15%). [7,8] Soft tissue contamination by the tumor, especially in Campanacci III stages and cases involving pathological fractures, increases the risk of recurrence. [9] While wide margin excision is known to yield the lowest recurrence rates, its application is limited by the benign nature of GCTs and potential for poor functional outcomes. Excision typically necessitates reconstruction methods such as arthrodesis, extensive bone grafting, or bulk and structural allografts. Extensive curettage has shown satisfactory control of local recurrence and favorable functional outcomes, making it a recommended treatment for GCTs. Intralesional curettage preserves joint integrity and enhances function without resorting to endoprosthetic replacements. Defects following curettage can be reconstructed using techniques like bone grafting, bone cement, or calcium phosphate. In this study, bone cement was employed for defect filling due to its ability to provide immediate structural support and prevent collapse. The benefits of cementation include its cytotoxic and thermal effects on tumor cells during surgery, allowing immediate full weight bearing postoperatively, and facilitating early detection of recurrence during follow-up. Concerns exist among some surgeons regarding potential degeneration of articular cartilage beneath weight bearing areas

treated with cementation. [2] It has been suggested that placing bone grafts beneath the cartilage may mitigate thermal damage caused by cement. Another issue associated with cementation is the presence of a radiolucent zone at the bone-cement interface. [10] In this series, most patients exhibited radiolucent zones surrounding the cement, possibly due to thermal injury or the mechanical properties of cement having a higher elasticity modulus compared to bone. While a sclerotic rim may form around the bone-facing cement, it typically does not progress and does not affect fixation. However, some authors argue that a radiolucent zone could potentially lead to micro motion between bone and cement, possibly resulting in fractures. [11,12]

In this study, none of the patients in the cementation group experienced postoperative bone fractures. We observed four patients with evenly distributed lucent zones around bone cement during the initial 4-13 months of follow-up (mean 8 months), which were suspected to be related to thermal burns caused by the cement. Subsequent follow-up indicated that these zones did not progress further. Research, such as that by Kafchitsas et al., has shown gradually progressive lucent zones between bone and cement in recurrent cases, suggesting ongoing evaluation is crucial. [13] Previous animal studies have demonstrated that replacing subchondral bone with bone cement does not compromise its strength. [14] Additionally, since articular cartilage nutrition primarily depends on synovium rather than blood

supply, the impact of bone cement on cartilage may be less severe than initially hypothesized. While the necessity and timing of internal fixation after bone cement filling require further study, our suggestion is that internal fixation is indeed necessary. Fraquet et al. have noted that without internal fixation, stress-induced loosening of bone cement could lead to further bone resorption and subchondral bone fractures, potentially resulting in a "bead effect" with the cement. [15] Internal fixation effectively locks bone cement and bone together, preventing loosening. In their study, the authors applied internal fixation in 16 out of 30 long bone GCT cases, observing no bead effect with the bone cement.

Toy et al. conducted in vitro biomechanical studies which demonstrated that bone cement filling of distal femoral bone defects, combined with internal fixation using cross screws, resulted in significantly greater biomechanical strength compared to simple bone cement filling or bone cement filling with intramedullary Steinmann pins. [16] Similarly, Ugliero et al. showed that bone cement filling of distal femoral defects, combined with internal fixation using steel plates, provided superior biomechanical strength compared to bone cement filling with intramedullary Steinmann pins or cross screws for fixation. [17]

Conclusion

Limb giant cell tumors (GCT) frequently affect the area around the knee, and many patients experience long-term survival, placing significant demands on limb function. This study concludes that while the distance between cement and subchondral bone may predict future arthrosis, it does not affect functional outcomes. Based on these findings, we recommend extended intralesional curettage, cauterization, and cementation with implant fixation following GCT curettage. This approach offers ease of implementation, optimal recovery of limb function, a low short-term recurrence rate, and high patient acceptance in clinical practice. With a median follow-up of 30 months in this study, further research involving larger cohorts and longer follow-up periods is warranted in the future.

Declarations:

Ethical approval: Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutes Ethical Committee

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